

POLYMERIC PESTICIDES FOR CONTROL
OF MARINE FOULING AND DETERIORATION

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Abstract

Research at the David Taylor Naval Ship R&D Center has led to the development and evaluation of a series of new polymeric pesticides capable of providing long life to such end item materials as ship bottom coatings, antifouling GRP composites, and preservatives for wood docks and pilings. These resins, known generically as Organometallic Polymers (OMPs), function in a manner which chemically controls the release, and therefore the retention, of pesticide in the end item product. As a result, long-lived products are achieved due to conservation of the pesticide, along with minimum environmental impact. Basic chemistry, mode of action, engineering properties of the resins, manufacturing scale-up processes along with performance data from ship and field trials of prototype end item products are discussed.

1. Introduction

Biologically active polymers, such as proteins, nucleic acids and polysaccharides, are the major macromolecular entities of all living creatures. It is not surprising then, that both natural and synthetic macromolecules, when modified by bioactive agents such as pesticides or pharmaceuticals, will effectively cause physiological responses when introduced into living systems. A new and vigorous technology known as "sustained" or "controlled" release is based upon such chemical modification and has resulted in improved, longer-lived products. An excellent summary of these new technological advances has recently become available [1].

2. Organometallic Polymers

An early development in controlled release technology was the generation of chemically bound, organotin containing resins at the David Taylor Naval Ship R&D Center [2,3,4]. These materials were targeted for use in antifouling bottom paints for Navy ships and general biodeterioration control. They comprise a series of acrylic, vinyl, polyester and epoxy resins which are chemically modified by the addition of trialkyltin and/or triaryltin pesticide and are generically known as Organometallic Polymers (OMPs). The chemical attachment of pesticide to polymer backbone provides for a slow controlled release (dosage) of pesticide to the surrounding environment.

Product service life is thereby increased. The OMPs were a major technology transfer item for the Navy in 1974. Since then, advanced development has taken place primarily with the acrylic OMP resins for use in bottom paints for Navy ships and wood preservatives for docks and pilings [5,6]. The latter application has already been demonstrated as an industrially acceptable impregnant for wood and a substitute for conventional creosote impregnation, providing not only improved biodeterioration performance, but also increased mechanical properties and structural stability to the wood [7]. In the coating application, progress has been slower, since here the OMP functions not only in pesticide delivery, but also as a binding resin in the coating. This requires certain high performance film forming characteristics necessary for maintaining the integrity of a coating in service aboard high speed Navy ships. Because of this, considerable emphasis is being placed on the Quality Control (QC) and Quality Assurance (QA) of the resin in order to optimize both the antifouling efficacy and resistance to erosion of the end product coating as well as to provide predictable performance and storage life of future production batches.

3. Bottom Coatings

Table 1 provides the basic formulae for two prototype OMP coatings which are currently undergoing ship trials. Note that in both paints, two OMP resins are used [8]. The OMP pigment is the reaction product of bis(tri-n-butyltin) oxide and a commercially available resin, Amberlite IRC-50 (Rohm and Haas Co., Inc.). It is a solid, and it is used as a toxic reinforcing pigment, providing control of paint viscosity and hardness, while also increasing pesticide loading. The OMP binder is a copolymer of tributyltin methacrylate (TBTM) and methyl methacrylate (MMA) in a 1:1 molar ratio. This resin functions as a co-binder in the coating as well as a pesticide delivery agent. The chemical character of the binder is critical to coating performance, especially film forming properties which are determined by the microstructure of the resin. Table 2 provides efficacy data on four OMP type binder resins in which the pesticide loading was varied through control of the TBTM:MMA ratio during synthesis.

Table 1
DTNSRDC OMP Paint Formulations
(percent by weight)

Ingredients	M253	M5211
OMP Binder (45% Solution)	35.57	28.67
OMP Pigment	27.36	11.47
Acryloid F10	6.84	9.55
Carbon Black	0.55	0.57
Silica	4.10	17.20
Bentone 38	0.68	0.72
Cab-O-Sil	-	0.86
Mineral Spirits	19.15	30.68
Xylol	1.37	-
Methanol	0.27	0.29
MIBK	4.10	-
	99.99	100.01
% Tin (Solids Basis)	22.61	13.49
Forecast Cost/Gal	\$34	\$31

Table 2
Fouling Performance of OMP-2 Type Binders

Mole % of TBTM	50			40			30			20
	5	8	14	5	9	13	5	11	13	15
Film Thickness (mils)										
Months 100% Fouling Free (Efficacy)	18	24	42+	30	42+	42+	42+	42+	42+	<12

As expected, the lowest pesticide loading (20 mole % of TBTM) showed incipient fouling in less than 12 months of exposure when tested on standard test panels at the semi-tropical, Miami Test Site. Thinner films of higher pesticide loadings provided increased efficacy. However, 5 and 8 mils film of the highest loading (50 mole % TBTM) showed incipient fouling in relatively short periods. The reason for this is that increasing the loading of pesticide negatively affects the film stability of the resin; after 18 months of submergence, little resin remained intact as a result of ablation of the film by the hydrolytic action of seawater. This should not be construed as a negative point for these resins since in the final coating, ablation is reduced by other coating additives (Acryloid F10) while pesticide loading remains high.

4. Resin Chemical Properties

Chemical data in Table 3 provides some information relative to the reproducibility of the OMP binder resin, produced in seven separate laboratory syntheses. Analytical information was prepared using the same equipment; variation in the data is obvious. Polydispersities of less than 2* are not expected to occur in the free radical polymerization by which this resin is produced. Most likely, limitations in the state-of-the-art especially for determination of M_w , M_n , or both are responsible. However, small amounts of very high M_w "microgel" can easily affect marked changes in M_w and must be carefully

Table 3
Chemical Properties of
50 Mole % TBTM Resins

Batch (Lab)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Number Average Molecular Weight (M_n , Daltons) $\times 10^3$	47	62	28	36	32	32	43
Weight Average Molecular Weight (M_w , Daltons) $\times 10^3$	92	63	420	170	62	67	61
Polydispersity (M_w/M_n)	2.0	1.1*	11.0	4.7	1.9*	2.2	1.5*
Intrinsic Viscosity (dl/gm)	.138	.134	.138	.140	.087	.114	.149
Viscosity Average Molecular Weight (M_v , Daltons) $\times 10^3$	46	44	46	47	24	35	52
Glass Transition Temperature (Kelvin)	259	279	277	268	277	281	277
% Tin	24.1	24.3	24.6	26.6	26.5	26.2	25.8

*See text.

avoided during processing. In an attempt to overcome these limitations, we are collaborating with the National Bureau of Standards in developing a standard methacrylate polymer as a control check for monitoring large-scale productions of this resin. While these data in Table 3 include traditional polymer characterization and provide suitable indication of polymer mechanical properties, they are insufficient for predicting antifouling performance. It is postulated that the OMP binding resins function through both a chemical reaction (hydrolytic cleavage of tin-oxygen ester bonds to free the pesticide into the environment) and physical dissolution of the residual tin-free binding resin (exposing fresh toxic surface for continued reaction). To relate polymer properties to this physical phenomenon requires more sophisticated polymer quantification and characterization, particularly to determine the microstructural properties of the resin. One goal in the synthesis procedure for example is to approach an entirely random distribution of pesticide within the molecular weight range of the resin. With the Bureau of Standards, a method for measuring the success in approaching this theoretical goal has been developed [9]. It must be recognized that testing such as this is necessary since the most important performance attribute of the coating, antifouling efficacy, cannot be quickly and accurately measured or predicted. Chemical characterization appears to be the only practical quality assurance method for assessing the acceptability of commercially produced batches of resin.

5. Scale-Up Resins

Early commercial batch productions of the OMP binder resin (125 and 250 pounds) in 1974 and 1975 were used in coatings formulation. Table 4 provides the chemical data and efficacy data now available. The resin from the 250 pound batch was used in the current ship trials coatings given in Table 1.

Table 4
Chemical Properties of Scaled-Up Resin
(50 Mole % TBTM)

	Batch 125 lbs	Batch 250 lb
Number Average Molecular Weight (M_w , Daltons) $\times 10^3$	84	98
Weight Average Molecular Weight (M_w , Daltons) $\times 10^3$	115	145
Polydispersity (M_w/M_n)	1.4*	1.5*
Intrinsic Viscosity (dl/gm)	0.446	0.324
Viscosity Average Mole- cular Weight (M_v , Daltons) $\times 10^3$	247	156
Glass Transi- tion Tempera- ture (k)	295	295
% Tin	20.2	23.2
Film Thickness (mils)	4	4
Months of 100% Efficacy	30	48+

*See text.

As can be seen, the larger batch of resins has provided superior antifouling efficacy; its choice for use in the ship trials coatings was fortuitous. Thin films (4 mils) have performed better than some of the earliest OMP binder resins (Table 2). When used as a co-binder in the coatings, this resin provided excellent coating materials, with good application and curing properties. Current ship trial data for both the M253 and M5211 coatings are extremely promising. Both coatings have been applied at dry film thicknesses of 4, 8, and 12 mils aboard both an Atlantic and a Pacific based combatant. To date, both coatings have provided 100% anti-fouling service after 33 months and 36 months, respectively, even at the 4 mils thickness. There is no evidence of coating erosion or loss in film thickness. Side-by-side comparison of these experimental coatings with conventional Navy standard bottom paint (Formula 121/63), which required mechanical removal of attached hard fouling during the ship trials, has demonstrated the marked superiority of these OMP

coatings. Since even the 4 mil coatings have performed well, it is likely that cost savings will include materials and labor for drydocking and painting as well as savings from decreased fuel consumption for ship powering.

6. Conclusions

OMP technology has produced a series of products offering immense improvement for control of marine fouling and biodeterioration. Certain resins such as binding resins for bottom coatings require close control and monitoring of chemical properties to assure high performance film-forming capacity as well as pesticidal efficacy. Because of the inability to accurately measure or predict efficacy in a short time period, chemical data and chemical standards are necessary for QA and QC in large batch syntheses. The fact that successful binding resins have already been manufactured in the commercial sector, combined with a reasonable availability of empirical performance data and chemistry data, indicate that a major breakthrough in coatings technology is imminent.

7. References

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